

A NEW SPECIES OF THE GENUS *OBRIMUM* DEJEAN, 1821 (COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE) FROM SICHUAN, CHINA

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ABSTRACT: *Obrimum angustum* sp. nov. from China (Sichuan) is described. The distinguishing characters are discussed.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, new species, taxonomy, China

The genus includes 20 Chinese species, but none of them is known from Sichuan. A discovery of Sichuan species fills a gap in the genus area in China between Shaanxi and Yunnan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 – 30.5 mm 1:2.8 – 4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustration were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Obrimum angustum, sp. nov.

(Fig. 1)

Type locality. China, Sichuan province, 70 km NW Chengdu, Qingcheng Hou Shan Mountains, 1400 m.

Description. Only one male available; body red-orange; antennae and posterior tibiae a little darker, but 1st antennal joint relatively pale; club-shaped apical parts of femora not darkened.

Antennae short, reaching elytral apices by 9th joint; 1st joint about as long as 3rd, longer than 4th and much shorter than 5th, which is about as long as 6th; first 4 antennal joints with several longer recumbent setae, other joints with very fine dense pubescence.

Head very wide, about as wide as elytra at base; eyes very big, coarsely faceted; the distance between upper eye lobes about 3 times less than width of each lobe; clypeus and especially frons with rather sparse punctuation.

Prothorax about 1.4 times longer than basal width, and about 1.15 times longer than width at big lateral tubercles; pronotum with slightly raised central elongated area sparsely punctated; pronotal punctuation rather big, but moderately dense; pronotal setae a little longer.

Elytra about 2.9 times longer than basal width, widened behind middle; independently rounded apically; a short elongated depression behind scutellum slightly pronounced; elytral punctation very distinct and moderately dense near middle, smaller at base and disappearing apically; pale elytral pubescence very short, semierect, nearly indistinct; elytral base without erect setae.

Femora strongly clavate; 1st joint of posterior tarsi about 1.4 times longer than 2nd and 3rd combined.

Last abdominal tergite rounded, last abdominal sternite truncated.

Body length 4.8 mm, width 1.2 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very close to *O. prosperum* Holzschuh, 2008 described from Yunnan because of very wide head with strongly exposed eyes, strongly elongated prothorax and relatively dark antennae; it differs by small, more elongated body, shorter antennae with pale 1st joint; 4th antennal joint shorter, than 3rd; larger femora clubs, which are much paler; denser pronotal punctation; smaller elytral punctation.

Material. Holotype, male, China, Sichuan prov., 70 km NW Chengdu, Qingcheng Hou Shan Mts., 1400m, 2-4.5.2006, S. Murzin & I. Shokhin leg. – collection of Maxim Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Etymology. The species epithet “angustum” means narrow in Latin.

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LITERATURE CITED

Holzschuh, C. 2008. Beschreibung von 60 neuen Bockkäfern und einer neuen Gattung aus der orientalischen Region, vorwiegend aus Laos und Borneo (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Entomologica Basiliensia et Collectionis Frey*, 30: 149-241, 65 figs.

Figure 1. *Obrium angustum* sp. nov., holotype, male, dorsal view.